

The Role of English as a Global Language

Polvonova Dildora Jumanazar qizi

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, 2nd year student

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Abstract: English is the most widely used language on globe. It is the only language that truly links the whole world together. It is a recognised official language in most of the countries. It contains rich literary treasures. Therefore, it is helpful for research work also good knowledge of English is required to access literature from hundreds of countries around the globe. It is the universal language that is used in the field of education, technology, internet, tourism and travel and employment also. It is not only considered the most important language for those who speak it as their first language but also for those who speak it as second language. English is essential to learn for seeking jobs or building career. In today's technology driven world, it is impossible to achieve academic or professional career without acquiring proficiency in English. This article enables a deeper knowledge of perspective towards the English language and its role not only in a particular country but also in another continent within the framework of globalization.

Keywords: English, global language, communication, good opportunities, language skills, foreign country, official language

Introduction

A language gains a global status when it develops a special role that is acknowledged in every country. This might seem like stating clearly obvious, but it is not obvious, for the conception of 'special role' has many facets.

There are two leading ways which can be made the official language of a country, to be utilized as a medium of communication in such domains as government, the law courts, the media, and the educational system. To gain in these societies, it is essential to master the official language as possible. Such a language is often used as a 'second language', because it is seen as a correlative to a person's vernacular, in other words 'first language'. The role of an official language is, in present time, best interpreted with English, which today has some kind of especial status in over seventy countries, such as Ghana, Nigeria, India, Singapore and Vanuatu. This is far more than position attained by other language – though French, German, Spanish, Russian, and Arabic are among those which have also developed a extensive official use. New diplomatic decisions on the matter continue to be made: for example, Rwanda granted English status in 1996.

Secondly, a language can be create a priority in country's foreign-language teaching, although this language has no official status. It becomes the language that children are mostly likely to be instructed and taught at their schools. If they arrive in school and the most available to adults who – for this reason- never learned it, or learned it partially, in their early educational years, it is also very important for the future of society. Russian language , such as , held

privileged position for 100 years among the countries of the former Soviet Union. Mandarin Chinese is also continues to play a especial role in South-east Asia. Today English is the language most broadly taught as a foreign or second language – in over 100 countries, in such countries as China, Russia, Germany, Spain, Egypt and Brazil – and in most of these countries and has already achieved as the dominant foreign language to be taught in many schools, often displacing another language in the process. In 1996, such as, English reinstated French as the premier foreign language in schools in Algeria (a former French colony).

History of English

English is a west Germanic language that was first used for speaking in early middle age England and is nowadays the most widely spoken language in the world. It is used as a premier language by the most people of several sovereign states, as the United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, Australia, Ireland, New Zealand as well as a number of Caribbean nations. Firstly, English arose in the Anglo-Saxon kingdoms of England and what is in present time southeast Scotland. Following the extensive effect of Great Britain and the United Kingdom from the 17th century to the mid-20th century, through the British Empire, and also of the United States since mid 20th century, it has been broadly extended around our planet, becoming the main language of international discourse and the lingua franca in many other regions.

From this statics appears questions why we need language, why it is so important to us. Without common language we can live or it is impossible to communicate with each other, In my opinion, it is possible with gestures or with pictures also as in Ancient Egypt, but innovations and establishing would not be like now. Consequently, we need language for linking and developing with other countries, in other words civilization. Thus, English is a language that creates connection with countries. In other paragraphs that would be given all information about these kind of role of English language.

In fact, language is tool for communication and people share their thoughts, feelings, ideas and expressions. In other words, language practices cultural transmission, socialization, position, sharing power, politics, and knowledge and so on. Although, there are various communication systems such as human communication system is well-recognized because of its arbitrariness, duality of patterning, displacement, voluntary-vocal and others. No language does not look like and all languages are has its difference from one another one with esteem to their popularity, traditions, dictions, influence, scope, aspects, facets, popularity, extra-linguistic distinction, standardization, status and so on.

English language and literature provides a solid foundation for developing critical thinking, analytical, and problem-solving skills. These abilities are highly valued by employers across various industries, making English majors attractive candidates for various job opportunities. Therefore, investing in English language studies is a wise decision for anyone looking to enhance their prospects for success in an increasingly globalized society. Whether pursuing a career in academia, business, or any other field, mastering English language skills will open doors to countless possibilities.

In present time, English is language that has own role in every fields of human beings. For example, in education, business, internet, tourism and travel that means for developing in this fields, first thing we need is English. Here I want to mention about some of the most important fields and role of English in them.

Education

Nowadays, Education is the thing that increases our status in society than it was. It is a known fact that English plays a special role in the field of education in our world. Because without this language we can not do anything in this life because everything is related to this now. It has become a compulsory to learn English the most important reason is now most of the books

of higher and primary education are printed in this language. English has been broadly utilized by the students, the teachers and researchers around the world as English is the predominant medium used almost in all fields of education and it is the only language where the most data is stocked in the some form of books and journals in published and electronic form too. As there have been alters in the field of educational system also, the students can make use of the resources useable around the universe just by accessing the internet. In addition, the learners can learn the subjects independently and develop self-learning attitude. In present, most of the students prefer to study in a foreign country for getting better employment chances all around the world and English will be a great plus for them. Therefore , the learners of English as a foreign language are promoted to learn English in order to advance their learning abilities in the fields as science and technology, IT, engineering, medicine, law, business as well as tourism. Because, there are all kind of more information in English than in other languages have that means everybody can establish in their field more than other people in your country. So, there is also a opportunity for students to improve their language skills and also with learning new information related to any subjects. Therefore, the significance of English in the field education is of widely use as most of the books are declared in English also many researches are done their paper work in English.

Employment

Another vital advantage of learning English is obtaining work with good salary as most of the job suppliers ask for the language skills, especially, communication skills in English. During the meeting also the interviewers test the candidates' communication skills in addition to their academic background knowledge. Even if the candidates' educational qualifications are excellent, the job suppliers pat attention mostly on their ability of directing ideas openly. As there are numbers of chances to work with the international organizations , everyone is trying to be the best while attaining the language skills in English. Once the job seekers should able to oral as well as written communication skills, that opens new doors for them that people could work anywhere all around world. Even most of the Chinese and the Japanese are trying to learn English for getting better employment opportunities in this world. Furthermore, nowadays in many countries, government give extra money from their salary, if they know and have certificate from this language. This is another good opportunity for linguists to increase their salary.

The Internet

The widespread of English as an international language with the advent of the internet as a mode of communication channel which has no limits, both are commonly forcing novel trends and bringing huge changes in this kind of globalization. Since the inception of the internet, it has brought drastic alters and made a revolution the ways of people's communication and their learning of their English language in the global context. The internet has become an vital linguistic medium as computer-mediated communication which is one of the basic factors of globalization. The internet has become significant for every aspect of our modern human life as the learning of languages. In 1960s, a new term 'global village' was coined by McLuhan (1962) and he further says, "Electronic communication will unite the world because "the medium is the message". Especially, these days almost everything is given in English, majority of bloggers also speak in English, even though their mother tongue another one, that is one another pushing factor to learn it in order to understand data on the internet.

Tourism and Travel

As travel and tourism is related to not only national levels, but also international degrees, English is the language that is widely utilized by all the international travel and tourism departments, agencies . when traveling to a foreign country, one of the most important thing is to know the language well of the that foreign country in order to communicate with the

people of the that you visited country, if you want to save money from guides. So there should be a the language that everybody can understand for the tourists to visit any country around the world and actually its one of the main purpose of global language. The international travel agencies' ambition at recruiting people who can communicate fluently with the tourists in English that means that is not only beneficial for people who want to travelling and save money without using it for guides, but also it helps for tourism. For example, in my country most tourists visit in order to learn more about historical places which are known as huge and unusual history. That is definitely profitable for both government and guides who explains tourists about our great history. In my opinion, tourism and travel has been developing in other countries as in my country.

Even in the scientific publications, English plays a special and predominant role as more than 80% of all scientific journal articles in 1998 were indexed by Chemical Abstracts and these were also written in English. Moreover, almost all the articles declared in natural science in 1996 were in English and 90% of the publications in humanities by 1995 were also in English. Now, English has become the prevalent language even in some non-English speaking countries as France, Spain and Germany. In this context, Adam Huttner-Koros says, "The academic papers outnumber in publications in the English language several times more than that of in their countries' own languages". It also shows that majority of scientists also want to produce influential, globally recognized work have to publish their articles and thesis in English as they have to share and strengthen their knowledge with other scientists around the world or by reading papers written either through their discussions in English. This is another proof of significance of English, not only speaking in this language, but also your articles in this language or thesis, any kind of research can help you to establish in your field and helps to get good status in your country too.

Conclusion

The importance and role of English as a common and global, language has been extensively discussed and most statistical information has been given as evidence to prove that English is the only language that is internationally used and accepted language. In this paper , the significance of English in education has been discussed in detail. Furthermore, the impact of the English language on the internet has been recounted as well as about the importance of English in travel and tourism has been elaborated. In conclusion, mastering English language skills is essential for unlocking global opportunities.

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